

**Bridging the security, privacy, and data protection gap for
smaller enterprises in Europe**

D7.3 - Dissemination strategy and activities – interim version

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Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
dKPIs	Dissemination Key Performance Indicators
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
EU	European Union
MS	Milestone
SMEs/MEs	Small and Medium Enterprises and Micro Enterprises
UI	User Interface
UX	User Experience
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

Deliverable D7.3 - Dissemination strategy and activities – interim version is produced within Work Package 7 (Ecosystem building, Exploitation and sustainability management) of the SENTINEL Project, under Task 7.2, Dissemination and communication strategy to trigger awareness and new business opportunities.

This document presents the SENTINEL's project dissemination and communication strategy and reporting of activities carried out during the first 18 months of the project. This follows the SENTINEL Milestone 3: First version of integrated platform of SENTINEL MVP, dissemination and exploitation reports (MS3) in which the project dissemination strategy and activities need to be reported. This deliverable will be updated and finalised in month 36 (D7.4).

The goal of the dissemination and communication concept is to identify and properly organize the activities needed to achieve the objectives of the project. Therefore, three main objectives have been defined:

- Develop the project's visual identity, including conventional information material, tools (project website, social media) and audio-visual material (e.g., videos, podcasts).
- Participate and organise outreach activities, international events (e.g., conferences and workshops) and INFO days.
- Develop solid dissemination and communication strategy and measures to be followed by the project consortium to raise awareness and reach to the relevant target audiences.

To assess the impact of the dissemination and communication activities, the dissemination KPIs (dKPIs) have also been analysed and presented. They will be monitored regularly to make sure that the project' goals and impact initially defined in the scope of the project are successfully achieved.

1. Introduction

Over 25 million European Small and Medium-sized Enterprises and Micro Enterprises (SMEs/MEs), central within EU enterprise policy, face multiple challenges related to personal data protection, ranging from awareness to a clear and practical roadmap to compliance. The most prominent one is the fact that, unlike larger enterprises, SMEs/MEs lack access to enterprise-grade cybersecurity technology and capacity-building for compliance, making them increasingly often victims of costly data breaches. SENTINEL aspires to bridge this gap by boosting SMEs/MEs capabilities in this domain through innovation at a cost-effective level. SENTINEL will be realised by integrating tried-and-tested security and privacy technologies into a unified digital architecture. Data from the modules of the SENTINEL architecture will then undergo disruptive Intelligence for Compliance through SENTINEL's digital core, featuring recommendations, policy drafting & enforcement for compliance and a 'one-stop-shop' incident response center.

Combined with a well-researched methodology for application, an open knowledge sharing hub and a wide-reaching plan for experimentation, SENTINEL will catalyse adoption of market-leading safe and secure technologies among SMEs/MEs and help safeguard their and their customers' assets.

1.1. Purpose of the document

The dissemination strategy and activities – interim version (D7.3), monitors and evaluates the SENTINEL's dissemination strategy and activities of the first half of the project period, including monitoring of the tools utilised to meet the activities scope, i.e. collaboration activities with other EU cluster projects, organization of events, publication of scientific results, active participation in social media channels, development of branding material (flyers, cards and roll-ups).

This deliverable, reports and analyses the results of dissemination through the indicators of success initially defined in the Grant Agreement.

Work Package 7 of SENTINEL (Ecosystem building, Exploitation and sustainability management) focuses on ensuring that the various outcomes of the project are widely disseminated to the appropriate target group, at the appropriate time and via appropriate methods. Furthermore, WP7 aims at identifying stakeholders who can contribute to the development, evaluation and uptake of the project outcomes and encouraged them to participate in the project's current and future actions.

The main objectives of WP7 are:

- Develop the project's visual identity.
- Raise awareness about the project concept, developments and findings to all key actors.
- Develop the dissemination and communication strategy of the project
- Develop the SENTINEL business model and strategies for incentivizing/promoting project adoption.
- Create a marketing strategy that focuses on commercialization.

1.2. Structure of the document

This document is structured in the following way:

Chapter 2: describes an overall dissemination and communication strategy to be implemented, including monitoring and reporting procedures. It also describes the dKPIs used to measure the impact of the dissemination activities.

Chapter 3: Highlights all events that were organized by the SENTINEL consortium members, as well as all third-party events which SENTINEL has participated in the M1-M18 project period.

Chapter 4: Presents the potential upcoming events where the SENTINEL partners intend to participate.

Chapter 5: Summarizes the material presented, presents the final remarks and concludes the document.

1.3. Intended readership

This document is intended for both consortium members and external stakeholders, since it comprises the SENTINEL strategy and the dissemination and communication activities performed within the first half of the project, and also includes the next upcoming activities.

2. SENTINEL Dissemination and Communication Strategy

2.1. Objectives

The aim of the dissemination and communication strategy is to take up the results of the project for the creation and support of a dynamic innovation ecosystem, targeting to achieve maximum visibility for the technologies and services developed for both technology-related communities and broader non-technical communities and the general public.

The engagement of technology providers, policy makers and end users during and beyond the end of the SENTINEL project will enable to create a self-sustainable future experimental and trial environment that will continue attracting the usage and attention of entrepreneurs and researchers. The dissemination and communication strategy of SENTINEL is schematically depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. SENTINEL dissemination strategy

2.2. Phases and timing

The main goal of the project's is to raise awareness on an individual and organisation level about the benefits of the SENTINEL platform and influence the view of a sufficient number of stakeholders, so that they will become aware of the project's new ideas, services and results, ultimately accept and adopt it. To achieve this goal the dissemination and communication strategy follows the three (3) phases shown in Figure 2 and briefly summarised below.

Figure 2. SENTINEL dissemination phases and methods

Phase-I: Brand awareness (M1-M12): this phase aims to promote the project, putting emphasis on awareness raising, ensuring that the project is appropriately recognized on a wide scale and securing an engagement of SMEs/MEs and any other interested stakeholder. During this period, the project's visibility was achieved by: redesigning the project logo which is the project's unique identity, designing and developing the project website, launching the social media profiles of the project, setting a clear communication and dissemination strategy and liaising with relevant projects and networks.

Phase-II: Knowledge Share (M13-M24): this phase focuses on development and understanding of project's technical specifications and requirements and the planning of various workshops. During this phase, the SENTINEL partners disseminate the projects results in different third-party events by pursuing further engagement with key stakeholders. Establishing contacts and relations with new stakeholders and initiating knowledge sharing with other similar projects is an important part of the current project stage. Within this phase, based on important milestone accomplishment, an updated set of various promotional materials (posters, newsletter, etc.) will support to spread a word and create new contacts.

Phase III: Market outreach (M25-36): this phase involves wide and effective dissemination of the project's tangible results, building on the project's favourable reputation and networking with the project target groups. Moreover, the project partners will motivate further participation of stakeholders in the project events (workshops, conferences) and promote exchange of experiences and knowledge sharing with related initiatives and take-up of the project results. Finally, it will also include the formulation of business model and go-to-market strategies.

2.3. SENTINEL target groups

The SENTINEL partners have already defined the project's relevant target audiences covering a full range of potential end users, groups and organisations of the proposed solution and categorised them in seven (7) specific groups. Each dissemination activity is tailored with a specific message to be conveyed to these groups:

- SMEs/MEs, business entities, companies, organisations (European and non-European) through the strong network of the pilot providers involved in this project: (i) Utilisation of the project's results in their everyday operations, (ii) Strengthening innovation by blending with in-house artefacts, (iii) Participation in the project's events, (v) Inspiration for new ideas and applications.
- Researchers and Academy members: Individuals engaged in research initiatives and/or working in research/academic institutes conducting core or application research cyber

ranges, ML-based technologies, cloud-based security services; (i) Further advancements on the above-mentioned technologies research through extension/reuse of the project's outputs in the investigated and in other application domains, (ii) Inspiration for future research initiatives based on the project's concept and results, (iii) Participation in the project's events.

- Security service providers/experts, technology clusters, and other innovation communities: (i) Inclusion of project's results to collaborative research activities (roadmap, white papers, position papers), (ii) Dissemination of project's results to their members, (iii) Bilateral participation in events for knowledge exchange.
- Policy makers (at any level like Ministries and Governments, Regulatory Agencies, Standardisation Organisations e.g., ETSI, CSCG): (i) Evaluation of the project's Social-Technological-Economic-Environmental-Political (STEEP) aspects, (ii) Definition of future research and innovation directions for national and EC initiatives, considering the project's acquired knowledge, (iii) Inputs for standardisation activities.
- H2020 projects' participants, partners and relevant stakeholders (including the projects funded under by EDA) related to security and privacy technologies and beyond: (i) Identification of common topics, (ii) Synergies and collaborations for results promotion, (iii) Enhancing innovation through results combination, (iv) Co-organisation of events, (v) Research Agenda formulation.
- General public (citizens): Individuals who benefit from the project outcomes, (i) Acquire new expertise and utilise the project results in scenarios that are addressed to the general public for gathering feedback, (ii) Increase general awareness.
- Investors: This is a crucial targeting audience from the exploitation perspective of the project. It includes angel investors and other private and/or public funds. In the case of SENTINEL project, their exploitation interest is purely commercial and depends on the partnerships and revenue agreement. They could invest in the delivery of the innovation to the market and (commercially) capitalise on this once mature.

Figure 3. SENTINEL target groups

2.4. Management

Managing and reporting dissemination and communication activities is very important for the successful implementation of WP7 and it demands the close collaboration of all partners. In SENTINEL, the dissemination and communication activities are coordinated by the Dissemination and Exploitation Manager (DEM) of the project. Mr. Ruben Costa from UNINOVA, as a DEM is responsible for coordinating the dissemination and communication activities during the project lifecycle. However, all SENTINEL consortium members are responsible for actively supporting and providing contributions to such activities.

With this respect, since the beginning of the project, monthly meetings have been executing on a regular basis, in order to discuss and plan the dissemination and communications activities to be executed within the project lifetime. Such activities can be identified as follows:

- Development and maintenance of the project's visual identity, including conventional information tools (project website, social media) and audio-visual material (e.g., videos). Considering this activity, the project website development and maintenance is under the responsibility of ITML, the social media channels (LinkedIn, Twitter and YouTube) administration are under the responsibility of UNINOVA, the publication of social media posts is under the responsibility of every partner. In order to facilitate the process of posting content in social media, the SENTINEL partners have agreed that every week each different partner is responsible for providing at least one post. Considering audio-visual material, the branding material (leaflets, roll-ups and business cards) creation was taken by UNINOVA, with respect to videos, the first SENTINEL promotional video was developed by ITML, with the support of UNINOVA. Also, UNINOVA has recently setup a series of interviews with domain knowledge experts, which are also available in YouTube.
- To raise awareness about the project concept, developments and findings to all key actors (the cybersecurity and data protection industry, SMEs/MEs, academics, policy makers, general public) by participating and organising outreach activities, international events (e.g., conferences and seminars) and INFO days. To raise awareness about SENTINEL, all consortium members have been fully engaged, by participating in different outreach activities and also disseminating the project's scientific results through paper publications in different conferences. For more detailed information about SENTINEL outreach activities, please refer to Chapter 3.
- To develop the dissemination and communication strategy of the project, including social presence, participation in EU events, collaboration with other related projects. With regards to this activity, all SENTINEL partners have been actively contributing. A more detailed overview regarding the dissemination and communication activities is described under Chapter 3 of this document.

2.5. Policy and rules

The policies for the dissemination of knowledge from the project (e.g., press releases and joint publications), along with the exploitation of foreground and background knowledge are clearly stated in Consortium and Grant Agreements. In particular, the SENTINEL Grant Agreement states that *“A beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give advance notice to the other beneficiaries of — unless agreed otherwise — at least 45 days, together with sufficient information*

on the results it will disseminate. Any other beneficiary may object within — unless agreed otherwise — 30 days of receiving notification, if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the dissemination may not take place unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard these legitimate interests”.

For dissemination actions, a common graphic identity is defined to allow for better visibility and recognition of the project. All dissemination material (deliverables, reports, presentation) include:

- the name and the logo of the project
- the website of the project
- acknowledge to EC public fund with the official EC logo indicating the Horizon 2020 below

With respect to publications, each partner should announce in a timely manner, to the dissemination manager and the project coordinator, the type (e.g., conference or journal article) and the context of the publication to be produced. This will allow checking if they fulfil the dissemination requirements or whether they conflict with other existing paper.

Every publication produced within the scope of SENTINEL is entitled to an acknowledgement section stating the following: *“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101021659”.*

2.6. Monitoring and reporting

Monitoring and reporting communication and dissemination activities is very important for the successful implementation of WP7 and it demands the collaboration of all partners. Therefore, partners will be responsible for undertaking their activities and reporting back to DEM. For this purpose, DEM has prepared and circulated a Dissemination Activities Reporting Template (see APPENDIX I – Activities Reporting template) to all partners requesting to complete the conducted activities.

For monitoring purposes, the dissemination activities are analysed and reassessed regularly by the DEM and incorporated to the corresponding project periodic reports. For purposes of evaluation of SENTINEL dissemination and communication activities, quantitative indicators and metrics have been already set up in Grant Agreement which are presented in Table 1 as well.

Table 1. Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for measuring dissemination and communication activities

SENTINEL Channels	KPI	Method of measurements	Frequency	Thres.	Results
SENTINEL website	dKPI#1: Number of visitors	Google analytics	Monthly	≥ 100	100
	dKPI#2: Number of page views	Google analytics	Annually	> 5000	5300
	dKPI#3: Number of downloads	Google analytics	Annually	> 500	421 clicks 244 down.
Social Media Twitter	dKPI#4: Number of followers	Twitter analytics	Monthly	> 20	16.8
	dKPI#5: Number of push announcements	Twitter analytics	Monthly	≥20	10.5

	dKPI#6: Number of unique visitors	Twitter analytics	Monthly	≥30	N.A.
Social Media LinkedIn	dKPI#7: New followers	LinkedIn analytics	Monthly	≥20	36.8
	dKPI#8: Number of push announcements	LinkedIn analytics	Monthly	≥20	12.5
	dKPI#9: New of unique visitors	LinkedIn analytics	Monthly	≥20	54
Brand-building materials	dKPI#10: Number of distributed hard copies of the SENTINEL brochure	Direct reporting	End of project	≥1000 distributed	450
	dKPI#11: Number of electronic SENTINEL brochures	Google analytics	End of project	≥1000 downloads	N.A.
	dKPI#12: Regular newsletters	Admin tool	End of project	≥ 9 newsletters	5
	dKPI#13: Number of SENTINEL videos and number of views	YouTube	End of project	3 videos with >1000 views each	5 videos, >200 views
Journal & magazine publications	dKPI#14: Number of international referred journal publications by SENTINEL partners	Direct reporting	End of project	>6	3 conference paper publications
	dKPI#15: Number of special issues in international referred journals	Direct reporting	End of project	>2	
	dKPI#16: Number of publications in international (printed or online) magazines	Direct reporting	End of project	>6	
Presentations in International Conferences	dKPI#17: Number of conference presentations by SENTINEL partners	Direct reporting	End of project	≥ 12	3
Third-party events (INFO DAYS, workshops, fairs/exhibitions targeting national & EU policy makers, potential stakeholders)	dKPI#18: Number of events	Direct reporting	End of project	≥ 15 events with >60 attendees	9 events
	dKPI#19: Number of audience contacts	Surveys	End of project	≥50% of the participants	-
	dKPI#20: Number of participants interested in SENTINEL project	Surveys	End of project	≥40% of the participants	-

SENTINEL Events (INFO DAYS, webinars workshops/demonstration events)	dKPI#21: Number of events organized by SENTINEL partners	Direct reporting	End of project	≥ 8 events with ≥60 attendees and 3 events with ≥100 attendees	6 events
	dKPI#22: Number of audience contacts	Surveys, interviews	End of project	≥50% of the participants	-
	dKPI#23: Number of participants interested in SENTINEL project	Surveys, interviews	End of project	≥50% of the participants	-
Liaisons and networking with the other relevant projects	dKPI#24: Number of SENTINEL members actively networking with other relevant projects	Direct reporting	End of project	≥ 6	11
Standardization/regulation relevant activities	dKPI#25: Number of “EAB” members monitoring and ensuring compliance with relevant regulations	Direct reporting	End of project	At least two (2) members of EAB	1

3. Dissemination and Communication Activities until M18

This section presents in detail the dissemination and communication activities carried out in the M1-M18 project period. During this period, WP7 focused its efforts on developing and implementing an appropriate dissemination and communication strategy and activities that will result in the best and most effective promotion of the project.

3.1. Dissemination activities

The following subsections outline the dissemination activities that have been executed in the M1-M18 period. The subsections gather a set of activities that with the combination of communication activities helped to share the project’s scope, objectives and results to the SENTINEL target audiences.

3.1.1. Scientific publications

Scientific publications are a broad-based dissemination tool and the SENTINEL academic partners joint efforts to strengthen the impact of dissemination activities by preparing and publishing scientific articles. The following table contains the publications authored by the SENTINEL partners that are directly related to the project.

Table 2. Publications in Conference Proceedings

Authors & Paper title	Conference Name	DOI/URL
Iosif Arvanitis, Grigoris Ntousakis, Sotiris Ioannidis, Nikos Vasilakis "A Systematic Analysis of the Event-Stream Incident"	EuroSec 2022 – 15 th European Workshop on Systems Security, April 5-8, 2022, Rennes, France	https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1145/3517208.3523753
Tatiana Trantidou, George Bravos, Philippe Valoggia et. al. "SENTINEL - Approachable, tailor-made cybersecurity and data protection for small enterprises"	IEEE-CSR 2022 - IEEE International Conference on Cyber Security and Resilience, July 27-29, 2022, Virtual	https://doi.org/10.1109/CSR54599.2022.9850297
Evangelia Kavakli, Pericles Loucopoulos, Yannis Skourtis, "Capability oriented RE for Cybersecurity and Personal Data Protection: Meeting the challenges of SMEs"	ESPRES 2022 – 9 th International Workshop on Evolving Security & Privacy Requirements Engineering, August 15-19, 2022, Virtual	https://doi.org/10.1109/REW56159.2022.00053

3.1.2. Dissemination events organized by SENTINEL

Aiming at sharing knowledge and engaging key stakeholders, multiple dissemination events have been organized by the SENTINEL partners which are listed in the table below.

Table 3. Events promoted by the SENTINEL Partners

Event	Date	Location	Partner
SME-centric Workshop I	16/09/21	Guimarães, Portugal	UNINOVA
SME-centric Workshop II	06/05/22	Hybrid	ITML/TSI
Webinar with Cluster projects	12/05/22	Online	ITML/UNINOVA
Webinar with PRODUTEC DIH	13/05/22	Online	UNINOVA
Workshop/Training with SMEs. MVP demonstration	26/09/22	Online	ITML/NETCompany
Digital Transformation Summit: SME-centric Workshop III	24-27/10/2022	Funchal, Portugal	UNINOVA

3.1.2.1. SME-centric Workshop I

The first SME-centric Workshop was organized by UNINOVA. It was focused on the GDPR and Data protection problems from SME point of view. As a first formal contact with SMEs, we had a long conversation about actual internal process, legal information, security policy and critical points of cybersecurity inside small and medium companies. In total, 12 participants external SMEs attended the workshop.

Figure 4. The SME-centric workshop I

3.1.2.2. SME-centric Workshop II

ITML and TSI in collaboration with PRAXI Network organized a workshop about GDPR compliance, cybersecurity, privacy and personal data protection for SMEs. It was a hybrid event, which was held live in Chania, Greece with the ability for companies to join the event also remotely, on the 6th of May, 2022.

The event was aimed at companies in every sector and covered topics related to GDPR, personal data protection and cyber security. GDPR compliance, its effect on SMEs' core business activities has been discussed during the event.

Figure 5. A digital banner of the SME-centric Workshop II

3.1.2.3. Webinar with Cluster Projects

On the 12th of May 2022, SENTINEL consortium has organized a joint clustering webinar with projects funded under the H2020-SU-DS02 and H2020-SU-DS03 topics to explore possible collaborations between EU-funded projects relevant to Cybersecurity, Personal Data Protection and GDPR compliance topics. More than 25 participants from PALANTIR, TRAPEZE, PUZZLE, CyberKit4SME, ARCADIAN-IoT, IRIS, ERATOSTHENES, IDUNN, and SECANT projects joined the event. It was a really brainstorming webinar with fruitful and constructive discussions from all the participants.

Figure 6. Webinar with Cluster Projects

3.1.2.4. Webinar with PRODUTEC DIH

On the 13th of May 2022, we conducted the 1st Webinar series with Portuguese SMEs, focusing on their concerns about data security, GDPR, and data privacy. We've started our engagement with 3 Digital Innovation hubs (ProduTech, DIH4CPS and DIHWorld). Such Digital Innovation hubs have supported the organization of this webinar entitled "The privacy and personal data protection in the national SME context". This particular webinar was set to create awareness on GDPR compliance and personal data protection at the Portuguese SMEs ecosystem and present the SENTINEL offerings. More than 70 registrations were subscribed in the event. The highlights of the event are available at SENTINEL YouTube channel. We appreciated the special participation of Rodrigo Adão da Fonseca who provided us with an overview of the GDPR scenario in Portugal.

Figure 7. DIHs webinar

3.1.2.5. Demonstration of the SENTINEL MVP

The workshop took place on the 26th of September 2022 with a total duration of 1.5 hour. In total six (6) participants (the SENTINEL use case owners (CG and TIG) and four external SMEs invited as part of Task 6.3 activities) attended the workshop. The aim was to assist the SENTINEL end-users to understand what the SENTINEL MVP is (scope, functionalities, the use cases etc.), and how to test it.

Figure 8. Demonstration of the SENTINEL MVP

3.1.2.6. Digital Transformation Summit/SME-centric workshop III

On the 25th of October, Sentinel organized the 3rd SME-centric workshop, co-located with the Digital Transformation Summit event, held in Funchal, Portugal. The main focus of the workshop was to present SENTINEL main objectives, including an interactive and demo session with hands-on at the MVP platform, followed by an interaction with the attendees, where it was described how SENTINEL offerings could be used by the SMEs. The workshop served as way to get quantitative feedback from the SMEs representatives, about the SENTINEL offerings, including the usability for the MVP presented. The Madeira's Digital Transformation Summit responded to the challenge of digitalization of Government, Infrastructures, Skills and Businesses in a forum where the EU's Digital strategy was debated to achieve the visionary objectives at European and regional levels.

Figure 9. SME-centric workshop III

3.1.3. Participation in third-party events

Within the period in which this document is concerned, SENTINEL also participated in several third-party events. The members of the consortium seized the opportunity to spread, (directly or indirectly), information about SENTINEL and develop a network among interested stakeholders in several dissemination events. These activities are listed in the table below:

Table 4. Third-party event participation

Event	Date	Location	Partners at Event
CyberHOT Summer School 2021	27-28, September, 2021	Chania, Crete, Greece	ITML, AEGIS, TSI, FP
IDC Security Roadshow 2022	20th April, 2022	Lisbon, Portugal	UNINOVA
15th European Workshop on Systems Security (EuroSec)	April 5-8 2002	Rennes, France	TSI
Transferable Research & Laboratory Outcome	28- 29, April- 2022	Lisbon, Portugal	UNINOVA
FIC Forum 2022	7-8, June, 2022	Lille France	ITML, UNINOVA, AEGIS, ACS
IoTWeek 2022	20-23, June, 2022	Dublin Ireland	ITML, IDIR
Policy to Projects Seminar (PPS)	30, June, 2022	Brussels, Belgium	ITML
INTEROP V-LAB General Assembly	30 June, 2022	Brussels, Belgium	UNINOVA
IEEE International Conference on Cyber Security and Resilience	27th July, 2022	Online	UNINOVA
9th International Workshop on Evolving Security & Privacy Requirements Engineering	15-19 August	Online	IDIR
CyberHOT Summer School	29-30, September, 2022	Crete, Greece	TSI, FP
Digital Transformation Summit	25-27, October, 2022	Madeira Portugal	all partners

3.1.3.1. *CyberHot Summer School 2021*

The Cybersecurity Hands-On-Training (CyberHOT) Summer School was organized by the Security Research Lab from the University of Piraeus, Greece and the Microprocessor and Hardware Lab from the Technical University of Crete, Crete. On this event the project was present ITML and FP, represented SENTINEL project at this event. The main objective was the dissemination and communication through the participants of hackathon and promote discussions about cyber security.

Figure 10. CyberHot Summer School 2021

3.1.3.2. *IDC Security RoadShow*

A day where the current topic “Security” was analyzed in all its aspects. At the IDC Security Roadshow, we had the opportunity to attend plenary sessions with several keynote speakers and participate in sessions focused on 4 essential topics related to the present and future state of the Security market: Security Operation Excellence Analytics and Orchestration, Data Privacy & Management, Next Generation Endpoint and Network and Next Generation Technologies.

The SENTINEL project participated in the event and carried out the dissemination among the participants with brief conversations about the project and distribution of communication materials

Figure 11. IDC Security RoadShow

3.1.3.3. 15th European Workshop on Systems Security

The 15th European Workshop on Systems Security (EuroSec) took place Rennes, France at April 5-8 2002, which brought together researchers, practitioners, system administrators, system programmers, and others interested in the latest advances in the security of computer systems and networks. TSI, participated in this workshop with a SENTINEL paper publication entitled "A Systematic Analysis of the Event-Stream Incident". The objective of the workshop is to discuss novel, practical, systems-oriented work. EuroSec encourages systems security researchers to share early iterations of bleeding-edge ideas with the community, before they are further developed into full papers. Reciprocally, authors receive feedback to help steer and improve their research to its full potential. Many EuroSec papers later form the basis for full conference papers presented at one of the top venues in computer security.

Figure 12. The banner of the 15th European Workshop on Systems Security

3.1.3.4. Transferable Research & Laboratory Outcome

SENTINEL was presented at the “Transferable Research & Laboratory Outcome” held on the 28th and 29th of April, 2022 by UNINOVA, in Lisbon, Portugal. In this event, there was a presentation of SENTINEL in one of the tracks dedicated to DIHs. During this event we have received an expression of interest from the “Digital Manufacturing Innovation Hub Wales”, to collaborate with SENTINEL, in order to test and validate our offerings.

Figure 13. Transferable Research & Laboratory Outcome

3.1.3.5. FIC Forum 2022

FIC is Europe's leading event on digital security and trust issues. It brings together the entire cybersecurity and 'trusted digital' ecosystem, including customers, service and solution providers, consultants, law enforcement and government agencies, schools, and universities.

This event took place in Lille, France, between the days 7th-9th of June, 2022. FIC 2022 is one of the events of the French Presidency of the Council of the European Union on digital security and trust issues. On FIC, SENTINEL participated with a booth and presented the platform and concepts of projects to visitors.

Figure 14. FIC Forum 2022

3.1.3.6. IoT Week 2022

IoT Week is an annual event organized by the IoT Forum since 2011. The IoT Week conference gathers industry and academia representatives from around the world. So far editions of the IoT Week were held, respectively, in Barcelona, Venice, Helsinki, London, Lisbon, Belgrade, Geneva, Bilbao and Aarhus.

The last edition attracted about 1600 participants specialized in the IoT domain, including research centers, research projects, large industries, SMEs, developers, standards development organizations and policymakers, including the European Commission.

Figure 15. IoT Week 2022

3.1.3.7. Policy to Projects Seminar – PPS

The SENTINEL project took part in the Projects to Policy Seminar (PPS) organized by the European Research Executive Agency from 30th June to 1st of July in Brussels. The event aimed at framing some of the key challenges in the policy, and cybersecurity areas of the European Union. The agenda of the event had several breakout sessions accompanied by interactive talks and open discussions about the focused topics. The SENTINEL project was presented as part of the Digital Security breakout session by elaborating on how the project offerings bring security and personal data protection for SMEs/MEs. It was a great event also from networking and liaison perspectives as the SENTINEL team met with representatives from TESTABLE, IRIS, ERATOSTHENES, SPATIAL, ARCADIAN-IoT, Secant, IDUNN, TRUSTaWARE, Electron, SOTERIA, CyberSEAS projects.

Figure 16. Policy to Projects Seminar

3.1.3.8. *INTEROP-VLAB General Assembly*

The SENTINEL value proposition was presented at the INTEROP-VLab General Assembly on the 30th of June, held in Brussels. UNINOVA is founding member of the I-VLab and presented SENTINEL main objectives and current achievements.

Figure 17. *INTEROP-VLAB General Assembly*

3.1.3.9. *IEEE International Conference on Cyber Security and Resilience 2022*

The IEEE International Conference on Cyber Security and Resilience (IEEE CSR) took place virtually, on the 27th of July 2022. IEEE is an annual event sponsored by the IEEE Systems, Man, and Cybernetics (SMC) Society. The conference focuses on theoretical and practical aspects of the security, privacy, trust, and resilience of networks, systems, and services as well as novel ways for dealing with their vulnerabilities and mitigating sophisticated cyber-attacks.

The Dissemination Manager of SENTINEL, Ruben Costa from UNINOVA, has presented a scientific article entitled "SENTINEL: Approachable, tailor-made cybersecurity and data protection for small enterprises". The subsequent talk focused on the role of the SENTINEL offerings in supporting SMEs/MEs to raise awareness, achieve data protection, GDPR compliance and boost their capabilities. Future steps, including further technical development of the SENTINEL's modules and contexts, as well as validation of various use cases in real-world settings, have been also presented and elaborated.

Figure 18. IEEE International Conference on Cyber Security and Resilience 2022

3.1.3.10. 9th International Workshop on Evolving Security & Privacy Requirements Engineering

The Evolving Security and Privacy Requirements Engineering (ESPRE) Workshop was held online between 15-19 August. This workshop is a multi-disciplinary, which brings together practitioners and researchers interested in security and privacy requirements. ESPRE probes the interfaces between Requirements Engineering and Security & Privacy and aims to evolve security and privacy requirements engineering to meet the needs of stakeholders; these range from business analysts and security engineers, to technology entrepreneurs and privacy advocates. IDIR has participated in this workshop, with a SENTINEL paper presentation, entitled: “Capability oriented RE for Cybersecurity and Personal Data Protection: Meeting the challenges of SMEs”.

Figure 19. 9th International Workshop on Evolving Security & Privacy Requirements

3.1.3.11. CyberHOT Summer School 2022

The Cybersecurity Hands-On-Training (CyberHOT) Summer School happened on Thursday 29th and Friday 30th of September 2022, under the auspices of the NATO Maritime Interdiction Operational Training Center (NMIOTC). The project was presented by TSI members (George

Hatzivasilis), who talked about the tools and features in the platform related to cyber-attacks and activities at this event.

Figure 20. CyberHOT Summer School 2022

3.1.3.12. Digital Transformation Summit 2022

The Madeira's Digital Transformation Summit occurred on October 25th - 27th and promote discussions about digitalization of cities which included the Data Security theme on them panels. Sentinel conducted a presentation of the project and promoted the technologies and solution developed and had great opportunity to create synergies with other projects and research institutions.

The Digital Transformation Summit responded to the challenge of cities digitalization in a forum where the EU's Digital strategy is debated to achieve the visionary objectives at European and regional levels. Bringing together recognized individualities from the European Commission, Government, Academia and Industry, The Summit sets the scene for a human-centric vision in a digital society. Discussing Horizontal Challenges for unlocking Digital Transformation potential. At technical side ranging from Artificial Intelligence, Big data and Cybersecurity and at Societal level including Digital Literacy, Skills and Social Inclusion.

Figure 21. Digital Transformation Summit 2022

3.1.4. Networking and liaisons with other relevant projects

The aim of this communication approach is to plan and implement joint activities with relevant projects, initiatives and networks. This was facilitated through various channels including the project website, but also the links and networking profiles of the SENTINEL partners that are part of several consortia and networks. Towards this effort, the relevant projects the SENTINEL project has established contacts so far are listed below.

Table 5. Networking and liaisons with other projects

Project	Partners	Further information
PALANTIR	ITML/UNINOVA	https://www.palantir-project.eu/index
ARCADIAN-IoT	ITML/UNINOVA	https://www.arcadian-iot.eu/
IRIS	ITML/UNINOVA	https://www.iris-h2020.eu/
PUZZLE	AEGIS/ITML/UNINOVA	https://puzzle-h2020.com/about/the-project/
IDUNN	ITML/UNINOVA	https://www.idunnproject.eu/
SECANT	ITML/UNINOVA	https://secant-project.eu/
CyberKit4SME	ITML/UNINOVA	https://cyberkit4sme.eu/
ERATOSTHENES	ITML/UNINOVA	https://eratosthenes-project.eu/
TRAPEZE	ITML/UNINOVA	https://trapeze-project.eu/
CONCORDIA	ITML/UNINOVA	https://www.concordia-h2020.eu/
CitySCAPE	ITML/UNINOVA	https://www.cityscape-project.eu/

3.2. SENTINEL communication activities

The communication plan gathers a set of strategically planned communication activities aiming at promoting the results of the project to a multitude of audiences (including media and public) in an effective manner and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange to ensure that the project stakeholders are properly informed about the objectives and offerings. In this context, a range of SENTINEL communication and promotion materials have been released during this time period and are uploaded to the project’s website:

- SENTINEL branding material (business card, roll-up, leaflet, poster)
- SENTINEL videos/podcasts
- SENTINEL newsletters

3.2.1. Branding material

The SENTINEL branding material developed within the first 18 months is presented in APPENDIX-II.

Table 6. SENTINEL branding materials

Type of Material	Link
Business card	https://nextcloud.sentinel-project.eu/index.php/f/5988
Roll-up	https://nextcloud.sentinel-project.eu/index.php/f/5988
Leaflet	https://sentinel-project.eu/sites/default/files/docs/BRO-CHURE_TRIFOLD_210X297_Real_Size.pdf
Poster	https://sentinel-project.eu/sites/default/files/docs/Sentinel-poster.pdf

3.2.2. SENTINEL videos/podcasts

Several video/podcasts have been created over the course of the M1-M18 project period and shared via the project’s website and YouTube channel. These materials are listed in the table below.

Table 7. SENTINEL videos/podcasts

Type of Material	Date	Link
SENTINEL video	Jun 2, 2022	https://youtu.be/rZChI-l8Glw
SENTINEL podcast I	April 28, 2022	https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLHZlexkZ7Dk3zyRe6-u8vYBiEB6bJu-5d
SENTINEL podcast II	Jun 16, 2022	
SENTINEL podcast III	Jul 25, 2022	
SENTINEL podcast IV	Oct 17, 2022	
Sentinel MVP	Oct 22, 2022	https://youtu.be/-bvjdw9fRjA

The next informative material is the SENTINEL newsletter. The purpose of releasing newsletters is to create a news item which can briefly illustrate the project updates. The newsletters described the project’s progress related to technical activities, project publications as well as other dissemination and communication activities. The material preparation was conducted by UNINOVA with the support and valuable inputs of all the partners. Proof-reading activities were conducted by ITML. The plan is to publish at least 1 edition every 3 months and increase our database of content.

Table 8. SENTINEL newsletters

Type of Material	Date	Link
Newsletter #1	September, 2021	https://sentinel-project.eu/dissemination-materials/
Newsletter #2	February, 2022	
Newsletter #3	May, 2022	
Newsletter #4	August, 2022	
Newsletter #5	November, 2022	

3.2.3. SENTINEL Website

The project website (<https://www.sentinel-project.eu/>) was created in M2 and is an informative and resourceful dissemination and communication tool of SENTINEL managed and hosted by ITML. It is a major channel of information and communication as it makes all of the project outputs freely available and readily accessible for visitors. Since its launch, the website is regularly updated to maintain a sustained interest in project activities. Updates highlight project news and events, paper publications, submitted and accepted deliverables, various promotional material.

Appendix II illustrates the website main screen with some important metrics filtered from google analytics.

3.2.4. SENTINEL Social media

The presence of the SENTINEL project in social media is one of the key actions for dissemination and communication activities. SENTINEL is presence in social network is enabled via three main social media channels namely, LinkedIn, Twitter and YouTube. The maintenance of these three channels is carried out by DEM. Regular posts and updates relating to the project’s developments and news, as well as reporting interesting news about project related topic have been published during the reporting period. Such activities have been used for interaction with both industrial and academic communities, and the general public, to provide information about the progress of the project and allowing for a means of a directly communicated feedback and information sharing mechanism. The website and social media channels’ main statistics for M1-M18 period are illustrated in Appendix III-.

We are planning to promote Sentinel on LinkedIn and generate leads with a paid campaign on the social media. The main objective is amplifying communication beyond small companies and disseminating the project to early adopters. To build the initial knowledge hub, we’ll need to process data from SMEs, and we are expecting to achieve enough companies with the Paid Campaign before M28.

Figure 22. Example of LinkedIn paid campaign configuration for events

4. SENTINEL Future Dissemination and Communication Activities

Evidently, while the consortium has made progress with respect to disseminating and communicating the goals and progress of the project to interested communities, further plan is needed in place for the last year of the project. To achieve this, the following subsections highlight the tasks and activities that are foreseen for the next project year.

4.1. Future planned dissemination activities

This section presents a list of potential dissemination activities (some of them already confirmed) that will be considered by the consortium members for the upcoming year.

Table 9. Tentative list of future dissemination and communication activities

Future events (Exhibitions, fairs, Info Days, Webinars, Workshop/Seminars, Conferences, Brokerages, Networking events etc.)	Date	Location	Link information
ENISA Cyber-Security Market Analysis (already confirmed event)	23-24/11/2022	Brussels, Belgium	https://www.enisa.europa.eu/events/cybersecurity-market-conference
Digital Health Summit 2022 (already confirmed event)	14-17/12/2022	Madeira, Portugal	https://www.hinnovahub.com/
Clustering Webinar on Cybersecurity (already confirmed event)	19/01/2023	Online	-
FIC Forum 2023 (already confirmed event)	5-7/04/2023	Lille, France	https://europe.forum-fic.com/
INFOSECURITY EUROPE	22/06/2023	Excel, London	https://www.infosecurityeurope.com/
IoTWeek	23/06/2023	Berlin, Germany	https://iotweek.org/
20th Annual International Conference on SMEs, Entrepreneurship and Innovation	24/07/2023	Athens, Greece	https://www.atiner.gr/sme
European Interdisciplinary Cybersecurity Conference	14/06/2023	Stavanger, Norway	https://www.fvv.um.si/eicc2023/
8th IEEE European Symposium on Security and Privacy	3-7/07/23	Delft, Netherlands	https://www.ieee-security.org/TC/EuroSP2023/cfp.html
36th IEEE Computer Security Foundations Symposium	10-14/07/23	Dubrovnik, Croatia	https://www.ieee-security.org/TC/CSF2023/
2023 IEEE Cybersecurity and Resilience	31/07/2023	Venice, Italy	https://www.ieee-csr.org/
Global Cyber Conference #GCC23	14/09/2023	Zurich, Swiss	https://swisscyberinstitute.com/conference/
CyberTech	3-4/10/23	Rome, Italy	https://italy.cybertechconference.com/
ECW (European Cyber Week)	TBD	TBD	https://www.european-cyber-week.eu/

4.2. Future communication activities

Entering the second half of the project's implementation, WP7 will continue to plan, implement different communication activities for the next project year.

4.2.1. Branding material

Two more newsletter issues and podcasts are planned to be released in the next project period (until M24).

- Newsletter Issue No. 6 (February 2023)
- Newsletter Issue No. 7 (May 2023)
- Podcasts

4.2.2. SENTINEL Website

The website will be regularly updated by publishing:

- Updates on project's progress, workshop, meetings, participation in conferences, etc. events related to the project,
- Public deliverables, reports, papers and promotional material.
- New dissemination and collaboration with similar projects.

Website analytics will continue to be used to monitor website visibility throughout the project's duration.

4.2.3. SENTINEL Social Media

The project social media profiles will be updated on a regular basis with:

- project news and developments.
- project branding material (new newsletter issues, podcasts, videos etc.)
- Deliverables and new publications.
- interesting quotes from partners about the project.
- articles from the web related to project topic.
- other developments from similar projects.

4.2.4. Collaboration with other similar projects

The project will continue its efforts in approaching similar projects and collaboration with other EU initiatives/DIHs and will regularly update established cross dissemination synergies.

5. Conclusion and Future Steps

This deliverable presents an interim version of the SENTINEL dissemination and communication strategy as well as activities executed in M1-M18 project period.

The objectives of the dissemination and communication activities are to integrate SENTINEL specific information with the requirements of the various market segments, through the dissemination channels. These activities involve the development of the project's visual identity (such as branding material, videos/podcasts, newsletters and any other promotional material). Further activities include participation and organisation of outreach activities (workshops, conferences, INFO days etc.). The aim of such activities is to achieve a substantial increase of the number of SENTINEL stakeholders that will actively participate in project's activities (e.g., requirements aggregation and consolidation and trials execution).

During the mentioned project period the consortium targeted at reaching the above-mentioned objectives of maximizing the project's visibility and spreading relevant information on the project's goals, activities and results. In this respect, the project partners produced a number of dissemination and communication materials (newsletters, leaflet, poster, business card, roll-ups video/podcasts) that were distributed via the project's online channels. Furthermore, the partners have participated in numerous activities (both online and physical participations) by informing and engaging with the scientific communities and business sector as well as relevant EU projects/initiatives.

SENTINEL has managed to execute most of its communication and dissemination activities. It is worth mentioning that the COVID-19 pandemic had a partial impact on the project dissemination and communication activities, in a sense that some events took place online thus limiting the full engagement of target audiences and key stakeholders.

To achieve successful and effective dissemination activities the SENTINEL consortium intends to increase the physical presence of SENTINEL in the second half of the project. Furthermore, as the technical results of the project become more tangible and robust, the dissemination and communication activities will be intensified via production of publications and scientific/technical outcomes. The results will be promoted during the second half of the project, with special focus on further partnerships with DIHs, EU projects and other relevant initiatives.

Appendices

Appendix - I: Activities reporting template

PUBLICATIONS

Partner(s) & Contact Person	Type of publication Journal / Magazine/ Conference paper	Estimated date of submission	Further information

ORGANIZATION OF EVENTS

Partners & responsible Person	SENTINEL EVENTS (webinars, workshops, special sessions, INFO-Days)	App. period	Further information

PARTICIPATION IN CONFERENCES

Partner(s) & Contact Person	Conference / Workshop	Date and location	Further information

PARTICIPATION IN EVENTS

Partner(s) & Contact Person	Any project relevant event (exhibitions, fairs, Info days, webinars, workshop/seminars, brokerages, networking events etc.)	Estimated date	Expected number of participants	Further information

DISSEMINATION MATERIAL

Type of dissemination material (newsletters, leaflets, brochures, posters, press releases, videos etc.)	Date	Responsible partner	Further information

NETWORKING WITH REVELANT PROJECTS

Partner(s) & Contact Person	Project name	Contact person of the other project	Further information/ Activity description

Appendix – II: Branding material, videos, podcasts, newsletters

SENTINEL Business card

SENTINEL poster

SENTINEL
 Bridging the security, privacy and data protection gap for smaller enterprises in Europe

The SENTINEL Offerings

- Intelligent Recommendation Engine
- Self-assessment and training portal
- Cybersecurity offerings
- Identity Management System for intelligent personal data processing
- A knowledge sharing hub - SENTINEL Observatory
- Policy Drafting Module

The SENTINEL Benefits

- Cost-effective solutions
- Simulation and training portal for cyber range assessment
- Tailored recommendations
- Personalised security offerings and mitigation tools

USE CASES

- Micro-enterprise case study**
 Implementing extra security measures for accessing genomic sequence and personal data from a bioinformatics platform-software pipeline.
- Small-Medium Enterprise case study**
 Homogenising the approach to data protection and compliance across multiple portfolio businesses through a single platform.
- SMEs/MEs engaged via Digital Innovation Hubs**
 Assessment of compliance regarding privacy and personal data protection within an ecosystem of SMEs and MEs

SENTINEL Consortium Members

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation program under grant agreement No 101021659.

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www.sentinel-project.eu
[@SentinelH2020](https://twitter.com/SentinelH2020)
[company/sentinel-eu-project/](https://www.linkedin.com/company/sentinel-eu-project/)

SENTINEL leaflet

SENTINEL at a glance

SENTINEL will bridge the security and personal data protection gap for European SMEs/MEs, by raising awareness and boosting their capabilities in the domain through innovation at a cost-effective level.

This vision will be realised by integrating tried-and-tested security and privacy technologies into a unified digital architecture and then applying disruptive Intelligence for Compliance.

Combined with a well-researched methodology for application and knowledge sharing and a wide-reaching plan for experimentation for innovation, SENTINEL will help small enterprises feel considerably more secure and safeguard their and their customers' assets.

OBJECTIVES

Develop and support a flexible, efficient and secure end-to-end digital Privacy and Personal Data Protection (PDP) compliance framework and Identity Management System (IdMS) for SMEs/MEs

Provide technological advances in automated data protection compliance assessment, such as tailor-made automated requirements engineering as a service, Machine Learning anomaly detection and recommendation systems and a Unified IdMS

Provide novel tools and services for enabling highly automated PDP compliance in SMEs/MEs

Validate, demonstrate and carry out experimental evaluation of the proposed framework on real-world SMEs/MEs operation scenarios

Raise awareness, collaborate with standardisation bodies and ensure technology transfer of project's results via EU digital innovation hubs

Boost the effectiveness of the EU data economy by offering high Technology Readiness Level solutions (TRL 6-7)

USE CASES

ClinGenics - A micro-enterprise

Implementing extra security measures for accessing genomic sequence and personal data from a bioinformatics platform-software pipeline.

Tristone Investment Group - An SME

Homogenising the approach to data protection and compliance across multiple portfolio businesses through a single platform

UNINOVA - SMEs/MEs engaged via Digital Innovation Hubs

Assessment of compliance regarding privacy and personal data protection within an ecosystem of SMEs and MEs

Consortium

The consortium consists of 13 partners from ten (10) European countries: Greece, Luxembourg, Belgium, Ireland, Switzerland, Germany, France, Portugal, United Kingdom and Malta.

Project Coordinator: Dr. George Bravos
 Institution: INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY FOR MARKET LEADERSHIP (ITML)
 Email: gbravos@itml.gr
 Start: 01/06/2022
 Duration: 36 months
 Participating organisations: 13
 Number of countries: 10

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SENTINEL
 Bridging the security, privacy and data protection gap for smaller enterprises in Europe

SENTINEL roll-up

SENTINEL newsletter

The graphic features a purple header with the SENTINEL logo on the left and the text 'Newsletter #2' in yellow on the right. Below the logo is the tagline: 'Bridging the security, privacy and data protection gap for smaller enterprises in Europe'. The main body of the graphic is yellow and contains a paragraph of text.

SENTINEL will bridge the security and personal data protection gap for European SMEs/MEs (small, medium and micro enterprises) by raising awareness and boosting their cyber capabilities through innovation at a cost-effective level. This vision will be realised by integrating tried-and-tested security and privacy technologies into a unified digital architecture and then applying disruptive Intelligence for compliance. Combined with a well-researched methodology for application and knowledge sharing and a wide-reaching plan for experimentation for innovation, SENTINEL will help small enterprises feel considerably more secure and safeguard their and their customers' assets.

The **SENTINEL** baseline

Given the broad scope of business processes, technologies and types of expertise involved, the SENTINEL baseline phase aimed to address the following questions: “which are the SME business and technical requirements with respect to Cybersecurity for privacy?”; “which are the system functional components that collaboratively satisfy these requirements?”; “what are the quality indicators, benchmarks and testing processes for evaluating the performance of the SENTINEL solution?”.

SENTINEL promotional video

SENTINEL podcast series

Appendix – III: SENTINEL website and social media¹

a) SENTINEL website

Event name	Event count	Total users	Event count per user	Total revenue
	21,683 100% of total	1,792 100% of total	12.10 Avg 0%	€0.00
1 page_view	8,010	1,773	4.52	€0.00
2 user_engagement	6,340	1,247	5.11	€0.00
3 session_start	3,572	1,751	2.04	€0.00
4 first_visit	1,774	1,772	1.00	€0.00
5 scroll	1,318	496	2.66	€0.00
6 click	421	114	3.69	€0.00
7 file_download	244	68	3.59	€0.00
8 view_search_results	3	2	1.50	€0.00

¹ The Reporting Period for social -media profiles is M1-M17.

b) SENTINEL LinkedIn page

Number of followers

Number of posts

Number of unique visitors

c) SENTINEL Twitter page

Number of tweets

Number of impressions

Number of visits

Number of new followers

